

Analysis Of Time-Use Pattern Among Rural and Urban Women in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Women in developing countries face time pressure due to multitasking and limited access to time-saving infrastructure, as they perform reproductive, productive, and community duties. This study investigates time-use patterns among rural and urban women in Ondo State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to profile the socio-economic characteristics of the urban and rural women, examine time-use patterns among respondents, and identify the key challenges faced by the respondents in managing their time. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used in the selection of respondents. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from rural and urban women. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. The results showed an average age of 36.11 years, with rural women being older than urban women; 55.33% were married, and 85.33% were employed, with rural women primarily in agriculture. Urban women were more educated and recorded higher incomes than rural women. Few of the respondents were members of cooperative societies. The results showed significant disparities in access to infrastructure. The majority of the urban women used gas for cooking, while most (67.33%) of the rural women relied on firewood. Furthermore, urban women spent a mean of 15.69 hours/day on various activities, while rural women spent a mean of 16.64 hours/day on various activities, with the overall mean of 16.17 hours/day on various activities indicating increased fatigue and stress on rural women. There were significant differences in the time spent on domestic chores, wage employment, and family business. Urban women spent slightly more time on ironing and child care, while rural women spent significantly more time fetching firewood and water. Urban women benefit from electricity and time-saving devices, while rural women face greater time stress due to limited infrastructure, multiple livelihoods, and heavy unpaid labor burdens. Lack of time management skills was common to all the respondents. The study recommends the need for targeted interventions like improved rural infrastructure, clean cooking energy, water access, and economic empowerment programs to reduce time stress and improve women's welfare, especially in the rural areas.

Keywords: Time-use, Rural –Urban divide, Women, Ondo State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Time use examines how people distribute their hours across various daily or periodic tasks and activities, exploring the balance between work, leisure, rest, domestic responsibilities, and other commitments. As an irreplaceable and finite resource, time grants everyone an identical daily allotment (of) 24 hours each day, equaling 8,760 hours annually (Ortiz-Ospina et al., 2020).

(While) global routines share commonalities, such as sleeping, working, eating, and leisure, notable differences emerge in individuals' autonomy to prioritize activities they find meaningful or they value most. Investigating global time allocation patterns sheds light on societal living standards, economic opportunities, and broader well-being (Ortiz-Ospina et al., 2020). Time-use research studies the distribution of individuals' time across daily activities and its impact on social and economic outcomes. (Ortiz-Ospina et al., 2020; Charmes, 2019).

Time-use patterns represent how people divide their 24-hour day between diverse activities such as paid job, unpaid care responsibilities, personal care, and recreation. Understanding these patterns is critical for uncovering hidden inequities, especially those founded in gender roles, socioeconomic status, and cultural expectations. (Arora, 2015).

In Nigeria both the urban and rural women face time constraints given a lot of productive and reproductive tasks. The unequal distribution of time among men, rural women and urban women can limit women's ability to engage in paid work, pursue education and training, and advance their careers, creating barriers to economic empowerment and independence. Traditional gender roles and expectations can impact women's time and contribute to the unequal distribution of domestic and care giving responsibilities, reinforcing gender inequalities. (Makama, 2024). Although several studies in Africa and Nigeria have identified significant gender disparities in unpaid care work, many of these investigations lacked comprehensive, disaggregated data and failed to adequately consider critical socio-demographic variables such as marital status, household structure, and occupational type (Badasi & Wodon, 2016; Adeyeye et al., 2019).

Preceding researches concentrates on national-level statistics, often overlooking community-level variances and so limiting the significance of their findings for localized policy creation. (Vickery, 2023; Charmes, 2020). Furthermore, few studies have applied a disaggregated urban-rural lens to time use, leaving critical gaps in understanding localized gender disparities (Charmes, 2020). Many overlook the burden of unpaid care work, especially in rural areas (Ferrant et al., 2014), and the overlapping demands of paid and unpaid labor (Hirway, 2017). Additionally, personal care time, vital for well-being, is rarely examined (Floro & Pichetpongsa, 2010).

These omissions limit the formulation of effective, context-specific policies (Esquivel, 2011; United Nations, 2020), which this study helps to address through its comprehensive, community-based analysis of women's time use pattern. In addition, time use patterns among other vulnerable groups [removed hyphen] such as youths, the elderly, informal sector workers, and female headed households- are often neglected. Emerging concerns, including the impact of climate-induced livelihood stress, digital labor demands, and inadequate care infrastructure, are also insufficiently explored. These omissions weaken the development of effective, context-specific, and gender-responsive policies (Esquivel, 2011; United Nations 2020). This study contributes to closing these gaps through a comprehensive community – based analysis that highlights the complex and unequal time burdens both urban and rural women face across multiple roles.

INTERSECTIONALITY IN TIME-USE STUDIES

Recent scholarship emphasizes the significance of an intersectional perspective, acknowledging that women's time use experiences are influenced by gender, class, education, income level, marital status, and place of residence. (Crenshaw, 1989; Folbre, 2023; UN Women, 2024). This perspective helps explain why rural women in Ondo State, who often have lower educational

attainment and larger households, face more severe time constraints than their urban, more educated counterparts, who benefit from better infrastructure and greater access to paid employment opportunities.

Evidence indicates that various social inequalities, including household composition, socioeconomic status, and resource access, amplify women's unpaid care responsibilities and increase time poverty. (Fawaz & Matei, 2021; OECD, 2022; Hochschild & Machung, 2012). Applying an intersectional lens, the study reveals that overlapping disadvantages compound time pressures, limiting women's opportunities for income generation, leisure, and personal development, moving beyond simplistic urban-rural comparisons.

These insights highlight the necessity for context-specific, gender-responsive policies that improve rural infrastructure, expand educational access, and reduce unpaid care responsibilities, benefiting time-constrained women more effectively than generic, one-size-fits-all approaches (UN Women, 2024; Folbre, 2023). Incorporating an intersectional approach enhanced the study's originality and ability to explain how intersecting social and economic inequalities influence women's daily time use in Ondo State.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area

The study was conducted in Ondo State, located in the southwestern region of Nigeria, bordered by Ekiti and Kogi States to the north, Edo State to the east, Oyo and Ogun States to the west, and the Atlantic Ocean to the south. Spanning a land area of 14,788.723 square kilometers, the state lies entirely within the tropics, positioned between longitudes 4°30' and 6° East and latitudes 5°45' and 8°15' North (Omonijo & Matzarakis, 2014). Established on February 3, 1976, from the former Western State, Ondo comprises 18 Local Government Areas (LGAs), divided into three agricultural zones: Ondo, Okitipupa, and Akoko. According to the 2006 census, Ondo State had a population of 3,460,877, with 1,745,057 males and 1,715,820 females. Projections by the State Bureau of Statistics estimate a current population of 4,883,792, including 2,462,525 males and 2,421,267 females. The capital, Akure, historically served as the seat of the Akure Kingdom and remains a cultural and administrative hub. The indigenous population predominantly speaks Yoruba.

Economically, the state relies on petroleum production, cocoa cultivation, and asphalt mining, with its extensive coastline supporting maritime activities. Agriculture plays a central role, with staple crops such as yam, cassava, maize, rice, plantain, and beans, alongside cash crops like cocoa and coffee (Ondo State Ministry of Information, 2016). The three agricultural zones reflect regional specialization in crop diversity, contributing to the state's mixed economy of natural resource extraction, farming, and trade. This socioeconomic landscape likely shapes time-use patterns, particularly in rural areas where agricultural labor and household responsibilities intersect.

Sampling Techniques

A multistage sampling procedure was employed in this study. The first stage involved a random selection of four local government areas out of the 18 local government areas in Ondo state. The selected LGAs [The LGAs changed to the Selected LGAs] include Akure North, Akure South, Ileoluji/Okeigbo, and Ifedore local government areas. The second stage involved a random selection of ten communities from the four LGAs.

The various communities include: Ijomu/Obanla, Oshodi/Isolo, Oke -Ijebu, Alagbaka Extension, Igoba, Ile–Oluji/Oke–Alafia, Ileoluji 11, Irese, Imo Irese and Ibule/Isoro. Urban communities include (Alagbaka Extension, Ijomu/Obanla, Oshodi/Isolo, Oke-Ijebu and Igoba first gate) while the rural communities comprise of (Ile-Oluji/Oke-Alafia, Ile-Oluji 11, Irese, Imo Irese and Ibule/Isoro).

Data Sources and collection

One hundred and fifty copies of a well-designed questionnaire were distributed to urban and rural women across selected communities in Ondo State. They were distributed in equal proportion, with urban women receiving seventy-five questionnaires and rural women receiving seventy-five questionnaires, to ensure balanced representation and comparability of time-use patterns between the two groups. The questionnaires were used to collect data on socioeconomic characteristics such as time-use patterns and occupations. [Number of questionnaire distributed added and the proportion indicated]. The survey included responses on household chores, voluntary work, care work, the labor market, and leisure activities. Also, data were collected on hours spent on daily activities and challenges faced by urban and rural women (financial constraints, social norms, access to technology, etc.). The questionnaire contains both open- and close-ended questions that cover various aspects of urban and rural women’s lives.

Method of Data Analysis

Analytical techniques used [employed replaced with used] to achieve the study’s objectives include descriptive statistics (frequency distributions and percentages, mean, median, and standard deviation).

Objective one: to determine the socio-economic characteristics of the urban and rural women was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency distributions, means, and percentages.

Objective two: to examine time-use patterns among respondents was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as (mean, median, standard deviation and variance).

Time use was determined by the number of hours spent on various activities by rural and urban women each day. Data on the primary uses of working time and the number of daily hours spent on various activities (0-24 hours) were collected from urban and rural women to compare working hours, average individual working hours, mean working time in urban and rural areas, and average total working hours. The entire time spent working, whether in the formal or informal labor market, doing home duties, or collecting water or wood. Time spent caring for sick and disabled household members, time allotted to employment, i.e., the amount of time spent assisting other households and in community services, was calculated using descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Socio-Economic Characteristics

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents based on their socio-economic characteristics. The table [Capital letter replaced with small letter in Table at second mentioning] revealed that the majority (32%) of urban women were between 41 and 50 years old, while an equal proportion (32%) of rural women also fell within this age range. The average age of urban women in the study was 38.0 years, whereas rural women had a higher mean age of 43.89 years. Overall, the mean age of all respondents was 36.11 years. This suggests they are in their prime working years, bearing

significant responsibilities. These findings align with the International Labour Organization (2023), which emphasizes that women in their productive years (typically 25–54) play a vital role in economic and household activities.

The table also reveals that majority of urban women (58%) were married, while 25.3% were single, 8% were widowed and divorced. Among rural women, 52% were married, 16% were single, 13.3% were divorced, and 18.7% were widowed. Overall, 55.3% of all respondents were married. This implies that married women face greater time burden due to combined reproductive and productive roles, especially in rural areas lacking infrastructure. According to Kabeer (2008), which highlights that married women often face greater time constraints as they juggle work and household duties.

The table also highlights household size distributions among respondents, showing that 94.7% of rural women and 88.0% of urban women live in households with 1–4 members. 91.3% of pooled sample fall within this range, with an average household size of 5 members. Rural women are slightly more concentrated in mid-sized households compared to urban women. Larger households are linked to greater caregiving and domestic management demands, which exacerbate time poverty, particularly for rural women who face limited access to infrastructure (e.g., childcare, clean water) and social services. Urban women, by contrast, may experience marginally lower time burdens due to better resource availability, such as labor-saving technologies. These patterns align with the ILO (2020), which underscores how inadequate infrastructure and larger household sizes disproportionately heighten women’s time poverty in rural contexts. Addressing these disparities requires targeted policies, such as expanding rural childcare facilities and improving infrastructure, to alleviate gendered unpaid work inequities.

The table also outlines the educational qualifications of respondents in the study. According to the table, disparity exists between urban and rural women: 54.67% of urban women had tertiary education, compared to 34.67% of their rural counterparts. Overall, tertiary education was reported by 44.67% of the all respondents. These findings suggest that urban women generally attain higher education levels than rural women, a trend consistent with Makama (2013) research linking gendered imbalances in time allocation to reduced educational access for rural women.

The table also presents the distribution of respondents by primary occupation. The result from the table revealed that the largest percentage (49.33%) of the urban women respondents were involved in trading and were self-employed, while a larger percentage (41.33%) of rural women respondents were involved in trading. These findings align with Makama (2013), who emphasizes women’s critical role in advancing societal and economic progress.

Table 1 also illustrates the distribution of respondents by their monthly income. According to the table, a larger percentage (69.33%) of urban women respondents fall within the income range of (less than 50000 - 50000), with an average monthly income of ₦55,554.1, whereas rural women had an average income of ₦44,121.6 and 84% fall within the range of (0 - 50000) naira. Furthermore, all respondents earned an average of ₦49,838.9. This means that urban areas have higher income levels than rural areas. This is consistent with Vickery (1977) finding that households require income to maintain non-poor consumption levels.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents according to their Socio-economic Characteristics

Variables	Urban		Rural		All	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)						
21 – 30	2	36	8	10.	35	23
	7	.0		7		.3
31 – 40	1	21	28	37.	44	29
	6	.3		3		.3
41 – 50	2	32	24	32.	48	32
	4	.0		0		.0
51– 60	4	5.	7	9.3	11	7.
		3				3
61 – 70	4	5.	8	10.	12	8.
		3		7		0
71 & above	0	0.	0	0.0	0	0.
		0				0
Total	7	10	75	10	75	10
	5	0		0		0
Marital Status						
Single	1	25	12	16.	31	20
	9	.3		0		.7
Married	4	58	39	52.	83	55
	4	.6		0		.3
Divorced	6	8.	10	13.	16	10
		0		3		.7
Widowed	6	8.	14	18.	20	13
		0		7		.3
Total	7	10	75	10	15	10
	5	0		0	0	0
Household Size						
(1-4)	6	88	71	94.	13	91
	6	.0		7	7	.3
(5-8)	5	76	55	73.	11	74
(9-12)	7	.0	2	3	2	.7
(13-16)	7	9.	2	2.7	9	6.
	2	3		2.7	4	0
		2.				4.
		7				0
Total	7	10	75	10	15	10
	5	0		0	0	0
Educational Status						
No formal Education	7	9.	12	16.	19	12
		3		0		.7

Primary Education	6	8.0	13	17.3	19	12.7
Secondary Education	1	24.0	23	30.7	41	27.3
Tertiary Education	4	54.7	26	34.7	67	44.7
Others	3	4.0	1	1.3	4	2.7
Total	7	10	75	10	75	10
	5	0		0		0
Primary Occupation						
Crop farming	3	4.0	26	34.7	29	19.3
Civil Service	1	17.0	5	6.7	18	12.0
Private services	3	.3	5	6.7	11	.0
Artisan	6	8.0	3	4.0	8	7.0
Trading	5	0	31	41.0	68	3
Others	3	6.0	3	3	9	5.0
None	7	7	2	4.0	7	3
	6	49.3		2.6		45.3
	5	8.0				6.0
		0				0
		6.0				4.0
		7				7
Total	7	10	75	10	15	10
	5	0		0	0	0
Monthly Income (Naira)						
≤ 50000	5	69.33	63	84	115	76.7
	2					
50001 - 100000	1	14.67	6	8	17	11.3
100001 - 150000	1	9.33	4		5.33	11
150001 - 200000	7	7.3				
200001 - 250000	2	28.57	1	1.33	3	2.0
	3	4	1	1.33		4
		2.7				
Total	7	100	75	100	150	100
Total income	5	4,546,000	3,365,500	38,201,000		
Average Income	5	5,	44,121.6	49,838.9		
	5					

Source: Computed from Field Survey, 2024

Time-Use Patterns of Urban and Rural Women in Ondo State, Nigeria

Table 2 shows the time spent (mean hour/day) on all activities by the urban and rural women. The [space added between dot and The] result from the table showed that urban women spent a mean hour of 15.69 hours/day on various activities while rural women spent a mean hour of 16.64 hours/day on various activities, with [wit h replaced with with] the overall mean hour of 16.17 hours/day on various activities. Similarly, Charmes (2019) found that rural women in Tanzania spent 13.2 hours per day on unpaid and paid work, compared to 11.1 hours per day for urban women. This is consistent with the present study's average of 16.64 hours per day for rural women and 15.69 hours per day for urban women. This is in line with Tadesse and Wondimagegn (2024) which found that women in rural Ethiopia face significant time constraints due to unpaid domestic responsibilities and labor-intensive agricultural tasks, limiting their participation in non-farm work, affecting their economic empowerment and overall well-being.

The study reveals a significant difference in time poverty between urban and rural women, indicating a higher time burden in rural areas due to unpaid labor and limited access to infrastructure and technology. This results in insufficient discretionary time for rest, leisure, and skill development, while urban women have access to better time-saving infrastructure and services. This is in line with ILO (2023) which highlights rural women's higher time burdens due to unpaid labor and limited access to infrastructure, emphasizing the need for targeted policies to alleviate time poverty.

Urban women spent a mean hour of (0.68 hours/day) on cleaning, while rural women spent a mean hour of (0.72 hours/day), with an overall average of (0.70 hours/day) on cleaning. Rural women spend more time cleaning than urban women due to limited access to cleaning technologies, but there is no significant difference in cleaning hours between urban and rural women. This is in line with Adeyeye (2021) which shows that rural Nigerian women face increased time burdens due to limited access to labor-saving technologies, affecting productivity and well-being, particularly in cleaning activities.

Urban women spent a mean hour of (1.15 hours/day) on washing, while rural women spent (1.17 hours/day) on washing, with an overall mean washing hour of (1.16 hours/day). The study shows that washing habits may not significantly differ between urban and rural settings, but urban women may have access to electricity, washing machines, and water. This is in line with World Bank (2021) which reveals a significant disparity in electricity access between urban and rural areas globally, with 83.9% of urban residents having access, compared to 24.6% in rural areas.

Urban women spent a mean hour of (0.23 hours/day) on ironing, while rural women spent a mean hour of (0.12 hours/day) on ironing, with an overall average of (0.17 hours/day) on ironing. Urban women face a significant difference in ironing time, possibly due to access to electricity, professional or social expectations, or higher participation in formal employment or public roles. This is in line with UN Women (2018) reports which highlight women's limited access to resources, particularly in rural areas, affecting their domestic work and unpaid care, emphasizing the need for quality public services and infrastructure.

Urban women spent a mean hour of (1.06 hours/day) on the market, while rural women spent a mean hour of (1.16 hours/day), with an overall average of (1.11 hours/day) on the market. The study indicates a minor rural-urban disparity in market time spent by women, with rural women

spending slightly more time due to longer market hours and limited proximity, while urban women may have shorter market hours due to convenience and infrastructure. There is no significant difference in market hours between urban and rural women. This is in line with FAO (2024). According to FAO, rural women often encounter limited access to resources, services, and infrastructure, which can increase the time required for various tasks, including market-related activities.

Urban women spent an average of 0.44 hours/day on fetching water, while rural women spent a mean hour of 0.66 hours/day on fetching water, with an overall mean hour of 0.55 hours/day on fetching water. Urban-rural disparity is attributed to infrastructure disparities, with poor infrastructure limiting access to water and limiting women's fetch water access, affecting income-generating and leisure activities. There is a significant difference in fetching water between urban and rural women. This is in line with UNICEF and WHO (2023). The WHO and UNICEF report highlights that women and girls aged 15 and older are responsible for water collection in 7 out of 10 households without on-premises supplies, disproportionately impacting their health, safety, and personal development.

Urban women spent a mean hour of (0.04 hours/day) on fetching firewood, while rural women spent a mean hour of (0.70 hours/day) on fetching firewood, with the overall mean hour of (0.38 hours/day). Urban women have better access to modern cooking fuels, reducing firewood collection, while rural women rely on traditional biomass due to limited alternative energy sources, resulting in significant time investment. There is a significant difference in fetching firewood between urban and rural women. This is in line with the International Energy Agency (2023). The International Energy Agency (IEA) emphasizes universal access to clean cooking by 2030 for health, environmental conservation, and gender equality, aiming to save 1.5 hours daily for households.

Urban women spent a mean hour of 0.59 hours/day on voluntary work, while rural women spent a mean hour of (0.58 hours/day) on voluntary work, with the overall mean hour of (0.59 hours/day). The overall mean hour of (0.59 hours/day) implies that both groups' daily activities are largely dominated by paid work, caregiving, or other responsibilities, resulting in voluntary work being a minor part of their routine. There is no significant difference in voluntary work between urban and rural women. This is in line with the World Bank (2021). The report emphasizes the need for comprehensive data on time use to improve women's economic opportunities and address time poverty.

Urban women spent a mean hour of 6.87 hours per day on domestic chores, while rural women spent a mean hour of 6.46 hours per day on domestic chores, with the overall mean hour of 6.46 hours per day on domestic chores. Urban-rural disparity in domestic chores suggests rural women may have additional responsibilities or structural inefficiencies due to limited access to time-saving infrastructure and energy-efficient cooking methods. There is a significant difference in domestic chores between urban and rural women. This is in line with Craig and Brown (2017). Craig and Brown's research reveals women often face greater dissatisfaction with balancing work and family life, despite increased paid work participation, due to disproportionate domestic responsibilities.

Urban women spent an average of 0.44 hours/day on child care, while rural women spent 0.26 hours/day on child care, with an overall mean hour of 0.35 hours/day on child care. This shows that urban women spend more time on child care than rural women, possibly due to better access to services and support, allowing them to engage in other unpaid labor or economic activities. There is a significant difference in child care between urban and rural women. This is in line with the World Bank Women Business and the Law (2021). The World Bank's "Women, Business and

the Law 2021" report highlights the importance of childcare availability in women's economic participation, highlighting the disproportionate burden of unpaid childcare responsibilities.

Urban women spent an average of 0.17 hours/day on child care, while rural women spent 0.24 hours/day on child care, with an overall mean of 0.20 hours/day on child care. This implies that rural women are found to spend more time caring for the elderly or sick, possibly due to disparities in access to caregiving infrastructure, social support systems, and cultural expectations. There is no significant difference in caring for old/sick between urban and rural women. This is in line with Crouch et al. (2017). Crouch et al. (2017) found that rural caregivers often have lower socioeconomic status, resulting in reduced income, education, and employment opportunities, potentially increasing caregiver strain.

Urban women spent an average of 0.26 hours/day on child care, while rural women spent 0.52 hours/day on child care, with an overall mean of 0.39 hours/day on child care. Urban and rural women face time disparities in caregiving, possibly due to structural differences in resources, cultural norms, and economic activities. Urban women may have more support and are more engaged in paid work, reducing their availability for unpaid caregiving tasks. There is a significant difference in caring for the disabled between urban and rural women. This is in line with Nancy Folbre (2020). Nancy Folbre's research highlights the significant impact of unpaid care work on women's economic opportunities and gender inequality, highlighting disparities in caregiving responsibilities.

Urban women spent an average of 0.95 hours/day on care work, while rural women spent 1.03 hours/day on care work, with an overall mean hour of 0.9 hours/day on care work. The study indicates a slight disparity in the duration of care work for urban and rural women. Rural women spend an average of 1.03 hours per day on care work compared to urban women, who spend 0.95 hours per day. This is in line with UN Women (2023). UN Women's 2023 reports show that women worldwide spend more time on unpaid care and domestic work than men, particularly in rural areas with limited infrastructure and time-saving devices. Urban women also spend slightly more time on these tasks.

Urban women have better access to infrastructure and childcare facilities, reducing their time spent on care work, while rural women rely more on their own labor for care-related tasks. There is no significant difference in care work between urban and rural women. This is in Crouch et al. (2024). Crouch et al. (2024) found rural children have lower odds of receiving preventive care and continuous health insurance coverage, highlighting disparities in healthcare access between rural and urban communities.

The study reveals a significant wage employment disparity between urban and rural women, with urban women spending more time (2.15 hours/day) than rural women (0.50 hours/day). The higher participation of urban women in wage employment leads to an average workday of 1.33 hours per day. This implies that urban women benefit from infrastructure, education, and market connectivity, while rural women face limited job opportunities and logistical barriers, often prioritizing domestic work over wage employment, leading to time poverty. There is a significant difference in wage employment between urban and rural women. This is in line with the International Labour Organization (2023). The International Labour Organization (ILO) reports that rural workers earn 24% less than urban counterparts, with half of this difference due to differences in education, experience, and occupation. The ILO suggests implementing minimum wage laws and equal opportunity policies to reduce these inequalities.

The findings indicate a minimal urban-rural disparity in the time spent on self-employment. Rural women (4.06 hours/day) and urban women (3.98 hours/day) dedicate nearly equal amounts of time to self-employment, with an overall mean of 4.02 hours/day. Rural women allocate more time to self-employment due to limited formal employment options and limited access to resources,

leading to a focus on agricultural or informal market activities. There is no significant difference in self-employment between urban and rural women. This is in line with the International Fund for Agricultural Development (2023). The International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD) emphasizes the importance of self-employment in rural economies, supporting rural microenterprises through technical, technological, and marketing assistance, enhancing income-generating activities for rural women.

The findings indicate a significant urban-rural disparity in the time spent working on farms or in family businesses. Rural women spend more than double the time (3.16 hours/day) on such activities compared to urban women (1.52 hours/day), resulting in an overall mean of (2.34 hours/day). Rural women rely heavily on agriculture and family-based economic activities for livelihood, often due to limited formal employment opportunities, while urban women have more diversified income sources, including wage and self-employment, reducing their reliance on these activities. There is a significant difference in work in farms or family businesses between urban and rural women. This is in line with FOA (2023). The 2023 report by the Food and Agriculture Organization highlights women's significant roles in agriculture, but calls for targeted interventions to improve their access to productive resources.

The findings suggest that there is negligible urban-rural disparity in the time spent by women on labor market work, with urban women spending 7.65 hours/day and rural women spending 7.72 hours/day. The overall mean is 7.69 hours/day, reflecting a nearly equal participation level between the two groups in labor market activities and economic necessity for women across settings to contribute to household income. Urban women may have formal employment, while rural women may engage in informal labor markets, potentially experiencing time poverty due to unpaid work, limited infrastructure, and lower productivity. This is in line with the International Labour Organization (2023). The International Labour Organization (ILO) reports a significant gender gap in female labor force participation, with a rate of 51%, 23 percentage points lower than men's (74%), especially in rural areas.

The study indicates a minimal urban-rural disparity in personal care time, with urban women spending slightly more time (1.09 hours/day) compared to rural women (1.02 hours/day). The overall mean of 1.05 hours/day implies that personal care is a small portion of daily schedules for both urban and rural women, with urban women spending more time due to better access to facilities and self-care routines, while rural women may spend less due to limited access to resources. There is no significant difference in personal care between urban and rural women. This is in line with the United Nations Development Programme (2023). UNDP 2023 study reveals minimal urban-rural disparity in personal care time, with urban women spending slightly more due to better facilities and routines, while rural women may spend less due to limited resources.

Table 2: Time Spent (Mean hour/day) on All Activities by the Urban and Rural Women T test for Difference in Mean Hours and Standard Deviation.

Activities	Urban Mean Hour/day	Rural Mean Hour/day	All Mean Hour/day	T test for difference in mean hours (t- statistics)	Two tailed p value
A. Domestic Chores					
Cooking	1.8 (0.64)	1.8 (0.64)	1.8 (0.64)	0.06	0.94

Cleaning	0.68 (0.24)	0.72 (0.16)	0.70 (0.20)	1.22	0.2 2
Washing	1.15 (0.52)	1.17 (0.47)	1.16 (0.49)	-0.35	0.7 5
Ironing	0.23 (0.34)	0.12 (0.09)	0.17 (0.25)	2.74* **	0.0 07
Market	1.06 (0.51)	1.16 (0.41)	1.11 (0.47)	-1.29	0.1 9
Fetch water	0.44 (0.33)	0.66 (0.27)	0.55 (0.32)	- 4.274 *	5.7 11 97 E- 05
Fetch firewood	0.04 (0.16)	0.70 (0.44)	0.38 (0.46)	- 12.63 *	4.7 8E -20
Voluntary work	0.59 (0.53)	0.58 (0.41)	0.59 (0.47)	0.19	0.8 4
Total Domestic Chores	6.46 (1.98)	6.87 (1.94)	6.46 (1.98)	- 2.59* *	0.0 1
B. Care work					
Child care	0.44 (0.61)	0.26 (0.42)	0.35 (0.53)	2.14* *	0.0 3
Caring for old/sick	0.17 (0.37)	0.24 (0.47)	0.20 (0.43)	-1.06	0.2 8
Caring for disabled	0.26 (0.85)	0.52 (0.45)	0.39 (0.69)	- 2.37* *	0.0 2
Total Care work	0.95 (1.06)	1.03 (0.75)	0.9 (1.06)	-0.87	0.3 8
C. Work in Labour Market					
Wage employment	2.15 (3.39)	0.50 (1.74)	1.33 (2.81)	3.67* *	0.0 00 44
Self-employment	3.98 (3.92)	4.06 (3.80)	4.02 (3.85)	-0.12	0.8 9

Work in farm or family business	1.52(2.66)	3.16(3.36)	2.34(3.13)	-3.41**	0.001
Total Work in Labour Market	7.65(2.15)	7.72(2.02)	7.69(2.07)	-0.23	0.81
D. Leisure					
Personal care	1.09(0.68)	1.02(0.75)	1.05(0.71)	0.64	0.51
Total Leisure	1.09(0.68)	1.02(0.75)	1.05(0.71)	0.64	0.51
Total Domestic Chores	6.46(1.98)	6.87(1.94)	6.46(1.98)	-2.59*	0.01
Total Care work	0.95(1.06)	1.03(0.75)	0.9(1.06)	-0.87	0.38
Total Work in Labour Market	7.65(2.15)	7.72(2.02)	7.69(2.07)	-0.23	0.81
Total time	15.69(3.37)	16.64(3.29)	16.17(3.34)	-1.77*	0.08

Note: Standard deviation in parenthesis. The t test compares the hour spent on each activities. Ho: There is no significant difference between the average working hour for all activities per day for urban and rural women. Null Hypothesis (H0) :urban = rural (Hypothesised mean =0). Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant difference between the average working hour per day for all activities of urban and rural women. H1: urban ≠ rural. Significant at 10 =;5% = **; 1% = ****

Source: Computed from Field Survey 2024

Key Challenges Faced by Respondents in Managing their Time

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents according to the key challenges faced in managing their time. The result from the table revealed that (56%) of the urban respondents do not have access to time-saving technology while (90.7%) of the rural women do not have access to time-saving technology. This is in line with the findings [the findings added] of Food and Agricultural Organisation (2018) that rural communities in most developing countries are more disadvantaged due to poor infrastructure compared to their urban counterparts. The [space added between dot and space] result from the table revealed that 94.7% of rural respondents faced financial constraints, while 21.3% of urban women faced financial constraints. This implies that rural women are more income poor than urban women. This is in line with Food and Agricultural Organisation (2024) that rural women face multiple obstacles to gaining independence and economic stability. The result from the table revealed that the majority (98.7%) of rural women face a lack of time

management skills more than their urban counterparts (78.7%). This is in line with Radhika Kapur (2024), who states that by prioritizing tasks and avoiding procrastination, rural women can better manage their multiple responsibilities, which is crucial for their personal and professional development. This is also in line with Kabeer et al. (2018), who state that rural women have to juggle multiple responsibilities because of their time poverty. The table revealed that the majority (96%) of rural women face challenges of social norms, while (68%) of the urban respondents face challenges of social norms. This is in line with Mzurana et al. (2021), who state that women's time poverty is influenced by social norms that dictate their roles and responsibilities within the household and communities.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents According to The Key Challenges Faced In Managing Their Time.

Key challenges Faced	Urban Frequency	Urban Percentage (%)	Rural Frequency	Rural Percentage (%)	All Frequency	Percentage (%)
Access to time saving technology						
No access	42	56.0	68	90.7	110	73.3
Access	33	44.0	7	9.3	40	26.7
Total	75	100	75	100	150	100
Financial Constraint						
No	59	78.7	4	5.3	63	42.0
Yes	16	21.3	71	94.7	87	58.0
Total	75	100	75	100	150	100
Lack of time Management skill						
Yes	59	78.7	74	98.7	133	88.7
No	16	21.3	1	1.3	17	11.3
Total	75	100	75	100	150	100
Social norms						
Yes	51	68.0	72	96.0	123	82.0
No	24	32.0	3	4.0	27	18.0
Total	75	100	75	100	150	100

Source: Computed from Field Survey 2024

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study provides a comprehensive analysis of time-use patterns among urban and rural women, revealing significant disparities driven largely by differences in infrastructure, access to labor-saving technologies, and socio-economic opportunities. Rural women were found to spend more time on daily activities (16.64 hours/day) compared to urban women (15.69 hours/day), indicating a higher time burden that could reinforce time poverty. This aligns with global research (Charmes, 2019; Tadesse & Wondimagegn, 2024) showing rural women's greater involvement in unpaid labor due to agricultural demands and poor infrastructure.

Significant differences were observed in specific activities such as fetching water, collecting firewood, wage employment, caregiving for the disabled, and domestic chores. Rural women consistently spent more time on labor-intensive and unpaid activities, while urban women benefitted from improved access to electricity, water supply, and formal employment. These findings mirror reports by international organizations such as the ILO, UN Women, UNICEF, and the World Bank, which emphasize the need for policy interventions targeting rural women's access to infrastructure and time-saving services.

On the other hand, some activities including washing, cleaning, voluntary work, and self-employment—showed minimal or no significant differences, suggesting that certain domestic routines cut across both rural and urban settings. The consistent gap in time spent on wage employment, however, highlights structural inequality, where urban women have more economic empowerment opportunities compared to their rural counterparts.

Overall, the study underscores the critical need for targeted time-use interventions especially in rural areas—through infrastructure development, provision of public services (such as water, energy, and childcare), and employment support. Reducing women's time burden is essential not only for their well-being and productivity but also for promoting gender equity and inclusive economic development.

The study recommends the need for targeted interventions like improved rural infrastructure, clean cooking energy, water access, and economic empowerment programs to reduce time stress and improve women's welfare, especially in the rural areas.

REFERENCES

- Adeyeye, T. (2021). *Labour-saving technologies and women's productivity in rural Nigeria*. Ibadan: Nigerian Institute for Social and Economic Research (NISER).
- Arora, D. (2015). Gender differences in time and resource allocation in rural households in Sub-Saharan Africa. World Bank. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/opendata/why-time-use-data-matters-gender-equality-and-why-it-s-hard-find>
- Badasi, B., & Wodon, Q. (2016). *Unpaid care work and girls' education: A review of the evidence*. World Bank Group Discussion Papers.
- Charmes, J. (2006). *A review of empirical evidence on time use in Africa from UN-sponsored surveys*. United Nations.
- Charmes, J. (2019). *Unpaid domestic and care work: Why and how to measure it*. International Labour Organization.
- Craig, L., Powell, A., & Smyth, C. (2012). Towards intensive parenting? Changes in the composition and determinants of mothers' and fathers' time with children 1992–2006. *British Journal of Sociology*, 63(3), 558–580. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-4446.2012.01427.x>
- Craig, L., & Brown, J. E. (2017). Feeling rushed: Gendered time quality, work hours, and life satisfaction. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 38(4), 431–444.
- Crenshaw, K. (1989). Demarginalizing the intersection of race and sex: A black feminist critique of antidiscrimination doctrine, feminist theory, and antiracist politics. *University of Chicago Legal Forum*, 140, 139–167.
- Crouch, E., Radcliff, E., & Bennett, K. (2017). Rural caregiving and health disparities in the U.S. *Journal of Community Health*, 42(4), 911–918.
- Crouch, E., McKinney, C., & Davis, S. (2024). Healthcare disparities in rural child populations: Access and utilization. *Journal of Rural Health*, 40(1), 88–97. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jrh.12612>
- Dong, X.-Y., & An, X. (2015). Gender patterns in housework and child care in China: 2004 to 2011. *Feminist Economics*, 21(3), 93–120.
- FAO. (2024). *The status of rural women in agri-food systems*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Fawaz, Y., & Matei, A. (2021). *Gender inequality in paid and unpaid work during COVID-19 times* (BSE Working Paper No. 1188). Barcelona School of Economics. <https://bse.eu/research/working-papers/gender-inequality-paid-and-unpaid-work-during-covid-19-times>
- Folbre, N. (2020). *The rise and decline of patriarchal systems: An intersectional political economy*. Verso Books.
- Folbre, N. (2023). Time poverty: Conceptualization, gender differences, and policy solutions. *Social Philosophy & Policy*, 40(1), 79–102. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0265052523000389>
- Hochschild, A. R., & Machung, A. (2012). *The second shift: Working families and the revolution at home* (20th anniversary ed.). Penguin Books.
- International Energy Agency (IEA). (2023). *Achieving universal access to clean cooking*.
- International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD). (2023). *Investing in rural people: IFAD's support for rural women's entrepreneurship*. <https://www.ifad.org/en/web/knowledge/publication>
- International Journal Corner. (2019). Gender inequality in time use: A study of selected rural communities in Ondo State, Nigeria. *The International Journal of Humanities & Social Studies*, 7(1).
- International Labour Organization. (2020). *Care work and care jobs for the future of decent work*.

- International Labour Organization. (2023). *World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends 2023*.
- Kabeer, N. (2008). Paid work, women's empowerment and gender justice: Critical pathways of social change. *Pathways Working Paper 3*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2513337>
- Leadership Nigeria. (2021). Gender equity and the need for reliable time-use data. *Leadership*. <https://leadership.ng/gender-equity-and-need-for-reliable-time-use-data/>
- Makama, G. A. (2013). Patriarchy and gender inequality in Nigeria: The way forward. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(17), 115–144.
- Nancy, F. (2020). Valuing care: Policies for unpaid caregivers and gender equality. *Feminist Economics*, 26(1), 32–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2019.1678549>
- OECD. (2022). *Persistent gender gaps in paid and unpaid work: Gender equality in a changing world*. OECD Publishing. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/gender-equality-in-a-changing-world_e808086f-en/full-report.htm
- Ortiz-Ospina, E., Tzvetkova, S., & Roser, M. (2020). Time use. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/time-use>
- Qi, L., & Dong, X.-Y. (2018). Gender, division of labor, and income inequality in Chinese households. *Review of Income and Wealth*, 64(3), 551–577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/roiw.12284>
- Ruggeri Laderchi, C., Saith, R., & Stewart, F. (2003). Does it matter that we do not agree on the definition of poverty? A comparison of four approaches. *Oxford Development Studies*, 31(3), 243–274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1360081032000111698>
- Sanghi, A., Sinha, R., & Mehta, P. (2015). Time use patterns and unpaid work in India. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 50(22), 17–20.
- Sousa-Poza, A., Schmid, H., & Widmer, R. (2001). The allocation and value of time assigned to housework and child-care: An analysis for Switzerland. *Journal of Population Economics*, 14(4), 599–618.
- Tadesse, T., & Wondimagegn, T. (2024). Time poverty and women's empowerment in rural Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Journal of Development Research*, 46(1), 45–62.
- UNICEF & WHO. (2023). *Progress on household drinking water, sanitation and hygiene 2023 update*. <https://www.unicef.org/reports/progress-on-household-drinking-water-sanitation-and-hygiene-2023>
- UN Women. (2018). *Turning promises into action: Gender equality in the 2030 agenda for sustainable development*.
- UN Women. (2023). *Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The gender snapshot 2023*. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2023/09/progress-on-the-sustainable-development-goals-the-gender-snapshot-2023>
- UN Women. (2024). *Progress on the Sustainable Development Goals: The Gender Snapshot 2024*. United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women. <https://knowledge.unwomen.org/en/resources/gender-snapshot>
- Vickery, C. (1977). The time-poor: A new look at poverty. *Journal of Human Resources*, 12(1), 27–48. <https://doi.org/10.2307/145597>
- Williams, J. C., Berdahl, J. L., & Vandello, J. A. (2016). Beyond work-life “integration.” *Annual Review of Psychology*, 67, 515–539.
- World Bank. (2021a). *Tracking SDG 7: The energy progress report*.
- World Bank. (2021b). *Women, Business and the Law 2021*. <https://wbl.worldbank.org/en/reports>